

An Analysis of the Memoirs of Marshal Louis Nicolas Davout

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Abstract: The following paper presents a first philological analysis of the memoirs of Marshal Louis Nicolas Davout, one of the key figures of all the Napoleonic Wars and of French history in general. The work is supported also by original elements of professional translation, which are provided with parallel text. The analysis starts from a linguistic and philological consideration, providing thus the author the possibility to chart a course into the historical context that gave birth to this work as well, highlighting its structure, content, and layout. Particular attention is addressed also to the presentation, translation, and comment of several different key extracts of the main historiographical and philological works about the historical personality introduced in the analysis. A further and extensive attention of historians, philologists, and linguists on the entire spectrum of available memoirs regarding the Napoleonic Wars, notwithstanding the overall interest and popularity all over the world, is still required.

Keywords: Davout, Memoirs, Siege of Hamburg, Bourbon Restoration, Memoirs of Marshal Davout

Citation: Rubini, F. (2023). An Analysis of the Memoirs of Marshal Louis Nicolas Davout. In W. Admiraal, E. Cakir, & M. L. Ciddi (Eds.), *Proceedings of ICHES 2023-- International Conference on Humanities, Education, and Social Sciences* (pp. 62-73), Amsterdam, Netherlands. ISTES Organization.

Introduction

Most of times, people tend to mistake the concepts of “memoirs” and “autobiography”: in order to better understand the philological and sometimes even historiographical difference between them, a good starting point can be the analysis of the linguistic definition of these two ideas.

According to “The Oxford dictionary of current English”, under the word “memoir” we find (Tompson, 1993):
“1. historical account etc. written from personal knowledge or special sources. 2. (in pl.) autobiography, esp. partial or dealing with specific events or people. 3 essay on a learned subject. [French *memoire*: related to MEMORY]”

Next, under the word “autobiography”, we find:

“1. written account of one's own life. 2. this as a literary genre.”

On the basis of this terminological difference between them, we can therefore conclude that, first of all, memoirs are an account of personal nature on a precise experience or period of somebody's life. Moreover, we can also rightly conclude, even if it is not expressly stated above, that memoirs are a subgenre of autobiography. In fact, an attentive study of memoirs can give the reader the possibility to fly back in time to different historical periods, to imagine and see how in the previous centuries people used to express their intentions, feelings, and thoughts.

This individual perspective today represents a key factor for those who desire to get into the psychology of the great personalities of the past, whose emotions, deeds, successes and mistakes influenced the course of history. By studying memoirs and documents of personal nature of these people in our days, especially with the use of modern technologies and means, we can realize that some aspects of their life appear even clearer to us than to their contemporaries; indeed, today we have the great advantage of knowing how a precise event of the past actually ended.

When Napoleon capitulated in 1814, for instance, the entire world was sure that he would never represent a threat to the European powers again, whilst today we know that in less than a year the "*hundred days*" would begin, culminating afterwards in the definitive and catastrophic French defeat of Waterloo in June 1815. Thinking about it now, as we can in 2023, such a story would have probably sounded bizarre, or even delirious, to anyone in April 1814.

The memoirs about to be introduced have little to do with the very character of Napoleon, but they belong to one of the most important characters of all the Napoleonic Era. Moreover, his part in this precise moment of history would not finish with these memoirs as a full stop. This preface is crucial to better identify the following topic: an analysis of the memoirs of Marshal Louis Nicolas Davout.

Method

The methodology choice made in the present work concerning the content of Davout's memoirs followed the guidelines expressed in the philological methods proposed by the University of Massachusetts Amherst, Robert D. Fulk (Fulk, 2016), and Christopher S. Mackay (Mackay, 1997), of the University of Alberta. This choice was made in order to study the presented text, the written records attached to it and to be able to establish and determine their meaning. The general translation method chosen in the work was the literary one, in order to convey the emphasis and the importance of several expressions, context, emotions, and tones present in the text. Nevertheless, the work required a wide use of professional, technical, and administrative translation as well. The first and the third mostly for the official acts and documents issued by government bodies, ministries, military administrations, and municipalities; the second, to a major extent, for the engineering, scientific, and military terminology.

Results

In a broad sense, Marshal Davout definitely cannot be considered a minor character of French history, nor of the Napoleonic Wars. As a matter of fact, the name of the “Iron Marshal” is on top of all search results on the internet when users look for the expression “the best marshal of France”; there is a huge quantity of forums, scientific papers, monographies, documentaries and blogs whose aim is to attempt to defend this thesis.

Of course, his name is not the only one, as all marshals of France, along with many other characters, contributed in the creation of the myth of the Napoleonic era. It is no coincidence that sometimes we even tend to generalize, identifying the expression “Marshals of France”, or “Napoleon’s Marshals” as something like a single whole. Besides, we have to consider that the concept of “being the best” sometimes appears quite faded and dull to be empirically demonstrated when it comes to historical research or philology.

Nevertheless, the overall interest and the plurality of the debates about this particular character testify a clear and widespread knowledge of this interesting historical figure. Unfortunately, Davout never left, as far as we know, a complete autobiography of his life; we have a relatively generous collection of his personal correspondence and various historical sources, along with several further biographies about him, which actually do help us in reconstructing the key events of his life.

The main of them, about his correspondence and his documents of personal nature, are without any doubt the following works:

- “*Le Maréchal Davout, prince d'Eckmühl, raconté par les siens et par lui-même*” (de Blocqueville, 1880).
- “*Le Maréchal Davout, Prince d'Eckmühl, Correspondance Inédite, 1790-1815, Pologne, Russie, Hambourg*” (de Blocqueville, 1887).
- “*Correspondance du Maréchal Davout, Prince d'Eckmühl, Ses Commandements, Son Ministère, 1801-1815*” (de Mazade, 1885).

The first of the previously mentioned works is a reconstruction of all the life of Davout, beginning from his early years up to his death, by the Marquise of Blocqueville, his last daughter. She was in fact a noblewoman of great culture, known for her fine mind, and whose salon in Paris was highly appreciated by the cultural élite of both the Second French Empire and the Third Republic.

This massive work, consisting of four volumes, was published in Paris between 1879 and 1880. In its dedication, at the beginning of the first volume, we can read the following words (de Blocqueville, 1880):

“Le nom du Maréchal Davout appartient au pays qui l'a vu naître, et non point à un parti quelconque : la

France a besoin de héros dans l'ordre moral aussi bien que dans l'ordre militaire ; je dédie donc ce livre à la mémoire de mon Père et à la France !

*Adélaïde-Louise d'ECKMÜHL,
Marquise de BLOCQUEVILLE, Paris, le 28 décembre 1878".*

("The name of Marshal Davout belongs to the country where he was born, and not to any party whatsoever: France needs heroes on the moral level, as well as on the military one; I dedicate therefore this book to the memory of my Father and to France!")

*Adélaïde-Louise of ECKMÜHL,
Marquise of BLOCQUEVILLE, Paris, December 28th, 1878")*

As we can clearly see here, the word "father" is written with a capital letter, in order to underline a form of respect.

The second work, also written by the Marquise of Blocqueville, was printed in 1887, that is, 7-8 years after the previous one, after having published "*Roses de Noël. Pensées d'hiver*" (1884) and "*Pensées d'un pape (Clément XIV), publiées par la M.ise de Blocqueville*" (1885).

Here too we can find an open dedication, even if much shorter, which reads (de Blocqueville, 1887):

"À la mémoire de mon frère, le Prince Louis d'ECKMÜHL, seul fils du Maréchal Davout qui lui ait survécu."

("In memory of my brother, Prince Louis of ECKMÜHL, the only son of Marshal Davout who survived him.")

These words were addressed to her brother, who had already died more than thirty years before, and with whom the name of the Princes of Eckmühl disappeared forever, having he passed away unmarried and without issue.

The third work presented in the previous listing is another massive gathering in four volumes of documents regarding the professional and personal life of Davout, curated by Charles de Mazade.

Particular attention deserve his last words about Davout in the preface of the book, just before the post scriptum (de Mazade, 1885):

"[...] Napoléon, le premier de tous, venait de mourir depuis peu dans son île lointaine. Murat avait péri fusillé en courant après sa couronne sur une plage de Naples. Berthier, la tête perdue, s'était jeté par une croisée d'un château de Bavière, en 1815. Lannes avait eu la mort des héros à Essling. Bessières avait été emporté par un boulet à Lutzen. Duroc avait été enlevé à Reichenbach. Desaix était mort depuis longtemps. Davout s'éteignait loin des champs de bataille, en pleine Restauration, à cinquante-trois ans. Il avait assez vécu pour rester une des plus fières et des plus saisissantes images d'une grande époque, du commencement du siècle."

("[...] Napoleon, first of all, had recently just died on his far island. Murat had been shot by firing squad running after his crown on a beach of Naples. Berthier, having lost his mind, had jumped out of a window of a

castle in Bavaria, in 1815. Lannes had seen the death of the heroes at Essling. Bessières had been struck by a cannon ball at Lutzen. Duroc had gone at Reichenbach. Dasaix was long dead. Davout faded out far from the battlefields, in the middle of the Restoration, at the age of fifty-three. He had lived enough to remain one of the proudest and most vivid images of a great time, of the beginning of the century.”)

Actually, Davout was one of the very few marshals of France who died of natural causes, though he passed away in serious illness, and several years after having overcome a period of disgrace.

Nevertheless, the only personal document he actually left for posterity are his memoirs to King Louis XVIII. This work was printed in Paris in 1814 after the abdication of Napoleon and the restoration of the Bourbons, after Davout had been cut off from France since the beginning of the siege of Hamburg (1813-14). This is a crucial point, because, notwithstanding the previously mentioned relatively widespread interest about the character, these only memoirs of him have never been translated. The only published translation ever made, from French into Italian, was realized in 2023 (Davout, 2023). The aim of this paper is therefore to present a first analysis of this work, which may represent an interesting scientific material for both philologists and historians in the future.

As we are about to analyze a memoir, first we need to determine the precise temporal interval, as well as the historical context, which are the object of the content:

« Sire,

J'ai l'honneur de soumettre à la justice de Votre Majesté l'examen détaillé de ma conduite ; Elle y acquerra la preuve que je n'ai jamais fait qu'un usage légitime de l'autorité dont j'étais revêtu. Je n'ai point abusé, Sire, du pouvoir qui m'a été confié ; aucun des actes de mon gouvernement, dans la trente-deuxième division militaire, ne peut être taxé d'arbitraire ; tous ont été dictés par des ordres ou décrets dont j'ai les originaux entre les mains, et dont je mets les copies sous les yeux de Votre Majesté.[...] » (Davout, 1814).

(« Sire,

I have the honor to submit to the justice of Your Majesty the detailed examination of my conduct; Your Majesty will obtain the proof that I only made a legitimate use of the authority of which I was invested. I never abused, Sire, of the power of which I was entrusted; none of the deeds of my command, in the 32nd military division, can be accused of injustice; all of them were imposed by orders or decrees whose originals lie in my hands, and whose copies I put under the eyes of Your Majesty. [...])

These are the very first words of Davout's memoirs. This *incipit* highlights the purpose of the work; Marshal Davout, in command of the 32nd French division, and cut off from France for several months, after a period of doubt has become aware of the proven capitulation of Napoleon and of the restoration of the Bourbons on the

throne.

Discussion

As we can see, in essence, Davout addresses to Louis XVIII a report of all the main events, his command, dispositions, and conduct during the siege of Hamburg, of which he was in charge.

The proof of it is provided in the attached documents, which confirm the receipt of the orders dated “April, 1813” from Prince Eugène, about his new dislocation, and the dispositions of Marshal Berthier, about the seizure and defense of Hamburg, dated “May, 1813”.

The following image (see Figure 1) shows the city of Hamburg, which Davout defended against the allied forces during the siege of 1813-14. Here we can easily see many of the recurrent geographical names present in the text, like “Altona”, “Hamburgerberg” or “Harburg”, which once identified on the map definitely help the reader in having a reference point about space and even military strategy.

Figure 1. A map of Hamburg in 1813-1814 (Neddermeyer, 1832)

Those who have read Davout's memoir without knowing the city of Hamburg can immediately notice the following key points on the map:

- The river Elbe in the southern part of the city, where the famous port is located.
- The strong line of fortifications on the northern side, oriented towards Altona, and stretching from Hamburgerberg to Lake Alster.
- The "Sternschanze", in the far northwestern part of the map.
- The eastern half-moon fortification line that extends from the southern bank of Lake Alster to the northern bank of the Elbe.
- The suburb of S. Georg, after the first eastern fortification line of Hamburg, occupying the lower bank of Lake Alster, and on this side of the second fortification line, before Hohesfeld.

Already in the opening pages of his memoirs, we can notice that most of Davout's arguments have as aim his defense against three precise accusations of which he has been informed, and from which he desires to clear his name:

« Le ministre de la guerre m'a annoncé (1) que Votre Majesté avait reçu des plaintes graves sur le commandement que j'ai exercé à Hambourg, et m'a ordonné, de sa part, de me justifier sur les inculpations qui me sont faites. Les principales sont :

1°. D'avoir fait tirer le canon sur le drapeau blanc, après avoir eu la connaissance certaine du rétablissement du trône des Bourbons.

2°. D'avoir enlevé les fonds de la banque de Hambourg.

3°. Et d'avoir commis des actes arbitraires qui tendaient à rendre odieux le nom français. Cette dernière inculpation est tellement vague puisqu'elle ne précise aucun fait, qu'il me suffira pour la détruire, de présenter le récit fidèle de mes opérations depuis ma rentrée à Hambourg, jusqu'au moment où j'ai reçu l'ordre de remettre à M. le général de division comte Gérard, le commandement de l'armée. » (Davout, 1814)

(«The minister of war announced me (1) that Your Majesty had received some serious denunciations about my command at Hamburg, and ordered me, from his side, to explain myself about the accusations moved against me. The main of them are:

1° Of having ordered the cannons to open fire upon white flag, after having received the certain knowledge of the return to the throne of the Bourbons.

2° Of having seized the funds of the bank of Hamburg.

3° Of having committed arbitrary acts that tended to make odious the name of the French. This last accusation is so vague, as it specifies no fact whatsoever, that in order to make it fall flat it will be enough for me to present the faithful account of my operations after my return to Hamburg, up to the moment in which I received the order to hand over the command of the army to count Gérard»)

This extract clearly explains the points which Davout desires to clarify, while in the same time we understand the ending point of the analyzed temporal interval, that is, the handing over of his command to General Gérard, which is proved by the attachment N°60, dated "May 11, 1814" (Davout, 1814).

The original edition of the book consists of approximately 170 pages, depending on the copy; the original from the Cantonal University Library of Lausanne, printed in Paris in 1814 by Crapelet publishing house, for instance, contains 159 pages of text, excluding the frontispieces and the empty pages.

Of these 159 pages, only about one third represent the very text of Davout's memoirs, which is not objectively that much, while the remaining two thirds are dedicated to sixty attached copies of documents of various kinds as a proof in support of the reasons expressed by the author.

About the documents attached to the main text, we can see that they amount to 60 units, which can be generally subdivided by content and layout as follows:

1. Correspondence – 39 units:

- a) Official service letters to Davout from French ministers and officers: correspondence and duty reports.
- b) Official letters between Davout and Russian army officials.
- c) Official service letters from Davout to French officials.
- d) Official letters between French staff officers and foreign officials.

2. Transcriptions (or their extracts) of French official acts – 9 units:

- a) Transcriptions of official minutes of the State Secretariat.
- b) Transcriptions of imperial decrees.

3. Davout's manifestoes, appeals, and agendas from Hamburg – 9 units:

- a) Appeals to the population of Hamburg and its officials.
- b) Appeals to the French army.

4. Manifestoes and appeals of Russian army officials – 3 units:

- a) Appeals to the population of Hamburg.

For a more accurate analysis of the documents attached to Davout's memoirs, also for the sake and the convenience of future researchers on this topic, we can report the following list of contents:

1. Attachment 1: Copy of a letter from General Dupont, Minister of war, to Marshal Davout, dated "*Paris, June 17, 1814*".
2. Attachment 2: Extract of a letter from Prince Eugène to Marshal Davout, dated "*Hoyenb, April 16, 1813*".
3. Attachment 3: Imperial decree of April 10, 1813, about the suspension of the constitutional regime in the departments of the 32nd division, dated "*Saint-Cloud, April 10, 1813*".
4. Attachment 4: Extract of an encrypted letter from Marshal Berthier to Marshal Davout, dated "*Waldeim, May 7, 1813*".
5. Attachment 5: Extract of the minutes from the State Secretariat, dated "*At the Imperial headquarters in Dresden, June 18, 1813*".
6. Attachment 6: Extract of a letter from Napoleon to Marshal Davout, dated "*Dresden, July 1, 1813*".

7. Attachment 7: Copy of the amnesty proclaimed in Hamburg by Marshal Davout, dated “*Hamburg, July 24, 1813*”.
8. Attachment 8: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to Napoleon, dated “*Hamburg, July 19, 1813*”.
9. Attachment 9: Copy of a letter from Napoleon to Marshal Davout, dated “*Bunzlau, July 7, 1813*”.
10. Attachment 10: Copy of a letter from Napoleon to Marshal Davout, dated “*Dresden, June 10, 1813*”.
11. Attachment 11: Copy of a letter from Napoleon to Marshal Davout, dated “*Dresden, June 10, 1813*”.
12. Attachment 12: Copy of a letter from Napoleon to Marshal Davout, dated “*Dresden, June 17, 1813*”.
13. Attachment 13: Copy of a letter from Napoleon to Marshal Davout, dated “*Dresden, June 17, 1813*”.
14. Attachment 14: Imperial decree of June 17, 1813, about the expenses of the 32nd division and its wages, dated “*At the headquarters in Dresden, June 17, 1813*”.
15. Attachment 15: Imperial decree of June 17, 1813, about the financial measures accorded to General Count Bourcier, dated “*At the headquarters in Dresden, June 17, 1813*”.
16. Attachment 16: Copy of a letter from Napoleon to Marshal Davout, dated “*Magdeburg, July 12, 1813*”.
17. Attachment 17: Extract of the minutes from the State Secretariat, dated “*At the Imperial headquarters in Dresden, June 17, 1813*”.
18. Attachment 18: Extract of the Imperial decree of December 24, 1811, about the organization and the duties of the general staff.
19. Attachment 19: Extract of the minutes from the State Secretariat, dated “*At the Imperial headquarters in Dresden, June 18, 1813*”.
20. Attachment 20: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to General Count Hogendorp, Governor of Hamburg, dated “*Ratzeburg, October 16, 1813*”.
21. Attachment 21: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to General Count Hogendorp, Governor of Hamburg, dated “*Hamburg, November 9, 1813*”.
22. Attachment 22: Appeal and Manifesto of Russian General Count Bennigsen, dated “*At the headquarters in Bergedorf, December 13/25, 1813*”(referred to the attachments N° 23 and 24).
23. Attachment 23: Appeal of Russian General Bennigsen entitled “*ORANGE BOWEN (Dutchmen!)*”.
24. Attachment 24: Appeal of Russian General Bennigsen entitled “*UNFORTUNATE PEOPLE OF HAMBURG!*”.
25. Attachment 25: Copy of a letter from Count Chaban to Marshal Davout, dated “*Hamburg, September 10, 1813*”.
26. Attachment 26: Copy of a letter from Count Chaban to Marshal Davout, dated “*Hamburg, September 15, 1813*”.
27. Attachment 27: Copy of a letter from Count Chaban to Marshal Davout, dated “*Hamburg, October 16, 1813*”.
28. Attachment 28: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to Count Chaban, dated “*Ratzeburg, October 18, 1813*”.

29. Attachment 29: Extract of the minutes from the State Secretariat, dated “*At the Imperial headquarters in Dresden, June 16, 1813*”.
30. Attachment 30: Copy of a letter from Napoleon to Marshal Davout, dated “*Dresden, July 16, 1813*”.
31. Attachment 31: Report from Count Chaban to Marshal Davout, dated “*Ratzeburg, November 2, 1813*”.
32. Attachment 32: Financial dispositions issued by Marshal Davout in response to the report of Count Chaban of November 2, 1813.
33. Attachment 33: Dispositions issued by Davout about the seizing of the Bank of Hamburg, dated “*At the headquarters in Ratzeburg, November 2, 1813*”.
34. Attachment 34: Extract of a letter from Count Chaban to Marshal Davout, dated “*Hamburg, November 5, 1813*”.
35. Attachment 35: Copy of a letter from Count Chaban to Marshal Davout, dated “*Hamburg, November 6, 1813*”.
36. Attachment 36: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to Napoleon, dated “*Ratzeburg, November 6, 1813*”.
37. Attachment 37: Decree issued by Davout about the replacement of Count Chaban after his death, dated “*At the headquarter in Hamburg, March 25, 1814*”.
38. Attachment 38: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to General Count Hogendorp, Governor of Hamburg, dated “*Ratzeburg, November 7, 1813*”.
39. Attachment 39: Copy of a letter from Danish Lieutenant Colonel Aubert to Marshal Davout, dated “*Altona, April 14, 1814*”.
40. Attachment 40: Copy of a letter from Russian General Bennigsen to Marshal Davout, dated “*Pinneberg, April 1 (13), 1814*”.
41. Attachment 41: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to Russian General Bennigsen, dated “*Hamburg, April 14, 1814*”.
42. Attachment 42: Copy of a letter from Danish Lieutenant Colonel Aubert to Marshal Davout, dated “*Altona, April 16, 1814*”.
43. Attachment 43: Copy of a letter from Count Blücher-Altona, president of Altona, to Colonel Higonet, dated “*Hamburg, April 20, 1814*”.
44. Attachment 44: Copy of a letter from Chief of Staff General de la Ville, to Colonel Higonet, dated “*Hamburg, April 20, 1814*”.
45. Attachment 45: Copy of a letter from Russian Aide-de-camp Prince Volkonskij to Russian General Bennigsen, dated “*Paris, April 1 (13) 1814*”.
46. Attachment 46: Extract of the Imperial decree of December 24, 1811, about the organization and the duties of the general staff.
47. Attachment 47: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to Russian General Bennigsen, dated “*Hamburg, April 22, 1814*”.
48. Attachment 48: Copy of a letter from Danish Lieutenant Colonel Auber to Chief of Staff General de la Ville, dated “*Altona, April 24, 1814*”.

49. Attachment 49: Copy of a letter from General de la Ville to Russian General Oppermann, General Bennigsen's Chief of Staff, dated "*Hamburg, April 26, 1814*".
50. Attachment 50: Order of the day, dated "*At the headquarter in Hamburg, April 26, 1814*".
51. Attachment 51: Copy of a letter from Russian General Oppermann to General de la Ville, dated "*Pinneberg, April 14 (26), 1814*".
52. Attachment 52: Copy of a letter from General de la Ville to Russian General Oppermann, dated "*Hamburg, April, 28, 1814*".
53. Attachment 53: Copy of a letter from Danish Colonel Aubert to General de la Ville, dated "*Altona, April 28, 1814*".
54. Attachment 54: Copy of a letter from General de la Ville to Danish Lieutenant Colonel Aubert, dated "*Hamburg, April 28, 1814*" (N.B.: The previous attachment states "*Colonel*", instead of "*Lieutenant Colonel*").
55. Attachment 55: Order of the day, dated "*At the headquarters in Hamburg, April 29, 1814*".
56. Attachment 56: Appeal of the Generals of the XIII Corps and the garrison of Hamburg to King Louis XVIII, dated "*Hamburg, April 30, 1814*".
57. Attachment 57: Copy of a letter from Marshal Davout to His Royal Majesty the Count of Artois, Lieutenant General of the Realm, dated "*Hamburg, May 1, 1814*".
58. Attachment 58: Order of the day, dated "*At the headquarters in Hamburg, May 5, 1814*".
59. Attachment 59: Copy of a letter from General Dupont, Minister of war, to Marshal Davout, dated "*Paris, May 2, 1814*".
60. Attachment 60: Order of the day, dated "*Hamburg, May 11, 1814*".

About the form of Davout's memoirs, as they are a formal appeal to King Louis XVIII, we can immediately notice that of course the syntax is relatively very complex, most of times characterized by very long sentences with several subordinate clauses.

The layout, in both the text addressed to the king and in almost all the attached documents, appears very formal and fascinating, maybe even with a strong taste of elegance and charm for the modern reader, which are given by the peculiar formulas of the time.

In this regard, there is a curious detail, which draws the attention of the attentive reader for its importance; in the text, there is a frequent grammatical incongruence in Davout's use of the apposition "*emperor*". Indeed, when he writes about Napoleon in the text addressed to the king (twenty-one times), he always uses the term "*emperor*" with a small "*E*", as if to express an already conscious distance from Napoleon, whilst in the correspondence provided by the attached documents we can often see a recurrent use of the same word, but with a capital "*E*" (fourteen times).

Punctuation deserves particular attention: the most extensively used punctuation mark in long sentences appears to be the semicolon, also on account of the very frequent listings and the formal terms of the text.

Vocabulary is generally complex; there is plenty of technical nouns and adjectives, whose nature ranges from the military sphere, passing through the juridical, economic, and political ones as well.

Moreover, at the end of the copy of 1814 quoted before, the reader can notice a page of *errata*, containing five *corrigenda*; this is an absolutely normal phenomenon, but still it deserves to be mentioned for the completeness of the description.

Conclusion

Marshal Davout's memoirs have thus recently become more accessible for a new part of readers, thanks to a first, at present, translation into a foreign language. Their content, consisting of important dates, documents, and thoughts expressed by his own hand, represents an inestimable material for historians, researchers, philologists and even simple enthusiasts of this precise historical period.

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